

Decoding CUDA Binary - Decoded Instructions

Here we provide a list of decoded instructions for the distinct ISAs we have explored. We enclose optional operands in parentheses. Operands use the names indicated by Figure 1. A specific operand name in the tables here correspond to a specific range of bits in Figure 1. We include official descriptions of the instructions from NVIDIA's CUDA Toolkit Documentation.

Compute Capabilities 2.x and 3.0

Compute Capabilities 3.x

Compute Capabilities 5.x and 6.x

Figure 1. Common operands on different CUDA architectures.

Instructions for Compute Capabilities 2.x and 3.0

Instruction	Official Description
VOTE (reg1), p6, p3	Query condition across threads
CCTL (reg1), [reg2 + 30-bit lit]	Cache Control
MOV32I, reg1, 32-bit lit	((undocumented))
MOV reg1, composite	Move
LDC reg1, const_mem_with_reg2	Load from Constant
SEL reg1, reg2, composite, p5	Conditional Select/Move
B2R reg1, 6-bit lit, p4	Barrier to Register
S2R reg1, special reg	Special Register to Register
P2R reg1, PR, reg2, composite	Predicate to Register
R2P PR, reg2, composite	Register to Predicate
TEX reg1, reg2, (reg3), 8-bit lit, 5-bit lit, tex, 4-bit lit	Texture Fetch
TLD reg1, reg2, 8-bit lit, tex, 4-bit lit	Texture Load

LEPC reg1	Load Effective PC
I2F reg1, composite	Integer to Float
I2I reg1, composite	Integer to Integer
F2I reg1, composite	Float to Integer
F2F reg1, composite	Float to Float
MUFU reg1, reg2	FP Multi-Function Operator
FLO reg1, composite	Integer Find Leading One
RRO reg1, composite	FP Range Reduction Operator
ISCADD32I reg1, reg2, 32-bit lit, 5-bit lit	((undocumented))
FADD32I reg1, reg2, 32-bit lit	((undocumented))
FMUL32I reg1, reg2, 32-bit lit	((undocumented))
IADD32I reg1, reg2, 32-bit lit	((undocumented))
IMUL32I reg1, reg2, 32-bit lit	((undocumented))
LOP32I reg1, reg2, 32-bit lit	((undocumented))
FADD reg1, reg2, composite	FP32 Add
FMUL reg1, reg2, composite	FP32 Multiply
DADD reg1, reg2, composite	FP64 Add
DMUL reg1, reg2, composite	FP64 Multiply
IADD reg1, reg2, composite	Integer Add
ISUB reg1, reg2 <-> composite	((undocumented))
IMUL reg1, reg2, composite	Integer Multiply
LOP reg1, reg2, composite	Integer Logic Op
SHL reg1, reg2, composite	Integer Shift Left
SHR reg1, reg2, composite	Integer Shift Right
BFE reg1, reg2, composite	Integer Bit Field Extract
POPC reg1, reg2, reg3	Population Count
FFMA reg1, reg2, composite <-> reg5	FP32 Fused Multiply Add
DFMA reg1, reg2, composite <-> reg5	FP64 Fused Multiply Add
IMAD reg1, reg2, composite <-> reg5	Integer Multiply Add
FCMP reg1, reg2, composite, reg5	FP32 Compare
ICMP reg1, reg2, composite, reg5	Integer Compare and Select
BFI reg1, reg2, composite, reg5	Integer Bit Field Insert
PRMT reg1, reg2, composite, reg5	Permute
FSET reg1, reg2, composite, p5	FP32 Set
ISET reg1, reg2, composite, p5	Integer Set
PSET reg1, p3/p5, p4, p5/p3	Predicate Set
FMNMX reg1, reg2, composite, p5	FP32 Minimum/Maximum
DMNMX reg1, reg2, composite, p5	FP64 Minimum/Maximum
IMNMX reg1, reg2, composite, p5	Integer Minimum/Maximum
VMNMX reg1, reg2, reg3, reg5	((undocumented))
ISCADD reg1, reg2, composite, 5-bit lit	Integer Scaled Add
VADD reg1, reg2, reg/lit composite, reg5	((undocumented))
BRX reg2, 24-bit lit	Branch to Relative Indexed Address
SSY 24-bit lit	Set Sync Relative Address
BRA 24-bit lit	Branch to Relative Address
PCNT 24-bit lit	Pre-Continue Relative Address
PBK 24-bit lit	Pre-Break Relative Address
CAL 24-bit lit	Call to Relative Address
JCAL 24-bit lit	Call to Absolute Address
TEXDEPBAR composite	((undocumented))
DSETP p2, p1, reg2, composite, p5	FP64 Set Predicate
ISETP p2, p1, reg2, composite, p5	Integer Set Predicate
FSETP p2, p1, reg2, composite, p5	FP32 Set Predicate
CSETP p2, p1, CC, p5	CC Set Predicate

PSETP p2, p1, p3/p5, p4, p5/p3	Predicate Set Predicate
LDLK p, reg1, [reg2 + 32-bit lit]	Load and Lock
LDSLK p7, reg1, [reg2 + 24-bit lit]	Load from Shared Memory and Lock
LD reg1, [reg2 + 32-bit lit]	Load from Memory
LDU reg1, [reg2 + 32-bit lit]	Load Uniform
LDL reg1, [reg2 + 24-bit lit]	Load from Local Memory
LDS reg1, [reg2 + 24-bit lit]	Load from Shared Memory and Lock
STL [reg2 + 24-bit lit], reg1	Store to Local Memory
STS [reg2 + 24-bit lit], reg1	Store to Shared Memory and Unlock
STSUL [reg2 + 24-bit lit], reg1	Store to Shared Memory and Unlock
ST [reg2 + 32-bit lit], reg1	Store to Memory
STUL [reg2 + 32-bit lit], reg1	Store and Unlock
RED [reg2 + 32-bit lit], reg1	Atomic Memory Reduction Operation
ATOM too complicated	Atomic Memory Operation
LD_LDU reg4, reg1, [reg2 + 6-bit lit], [reg3 + 6-bit lit]	A combination of a generic load LD with a load uniform LDU
NOP (CC)	No Operation
CONT	Continue in Loop
BRK	Break from Loop
RET	Return from Call
EXIT	Exit Program
BPT	Breakpoint/Trap
MEMBAR	Memory Barrier

Instructions for Compute Capability 3.x

Instruction	Official Description
FCHK p2, reg2, composite	FP32 Division Test
VOTE (reg1), p6, p5	Query condition across threads
LDC reg1, const_mem_with_reg2	Load Constant
MOV reg1, composite, (5-bit lit)	Move
MOV32I reg1, 32-bit lit, (4-bit lit)	((undocumented))
S2R reg1, special reg	Move Special Register to Register
P2R reg1, PR, reg2, composite	Predicate to Register
R2P PR, reg1, composite	Register to Predicate
SEL reg1, reg2, composite, p5	Conditional Select/Move
TEX reg1, reg2, (reg3), 14-bit lit, tex, 4-bit lit	Texture Fetch
TLD reg1, reg2, (reg3), 15-bit lit tex, 4-bit lit	Texture Load
F2F reg1, composite	Floating Point To Floating Point Conversion
F2I reg1, composite	Floating Point To Integer Conversion
I2F reg1, composite	Integer To Floating Point Conversion
I2I reg1, composite	Integer To Integer Conversion
MUFU reg1, reg2	FP32 Multi Function Operation
FLO reg1, composite	Find Leading One
RRO reg1, composite	Range Reduction Operator FP
FADD32I reg1, reg2, 32-bit lit	((undocumented))
FMUL32I reg1, reg2, 32-bit lit	((undocumented))
IADD32I reg1, reg2, 32-bit lit	((undocumented))
IMUL32I reg1, reg2, 32-bit lit	((undocumented))
LOP32I reg1, reg2, 32-bit lit	((undocumented))
BFE reg1, reg2, composite	Integer Bit Field Extract
IADD reg1, reg2, composite	Integer Addition
IMUL reg1, reg2, composite	Integer Multiply
ISUB reg1, composite, reg2	((undocumented))

ISUB reg1, reg2, composite	((undocumented))
DADD reg1, reg2, composite	FP64 Add
DMUL reg1, reg2, composite	FP64 Multiply
FADD reg1, reg2, composite	FP32 Add
FMUL reg1, reg2, composite	FP32 Multiply
LOP reg1, reg2, composite	Integer Logic Op
POPC reg1, reg2, composite	Population Count
SHL reg1, reg2, composite	Integer Shift Left
SHR reg1, reg2, composite	Integer Shift Right
ISET reg1, reg2, composite, p5	Integer Set
PSET reg1, p3, p4, p5	Predicate Set
DFMA reg1, reg2, composite <-> reg4	FP64 Fused Multiply Add
FFMA reg1, reg2, composite <-> reg4	FP32 Fused Multiply Add
IMAD reg1, reg2, composite <-> reg4	Integer Multiply And Add
DMNMX reg1, reg2, composite, p5	FP64 Minimum/Maximum
FMNMX reg1, reg2, composite, p5	FP32 Minimum/Maximum
IMNMX reg1, reg2, composite, p5	Integer Minimum/Maximum
BFI reg1, reg2, composite, reg4	Integer Bit Field Insert
PRMT reg1, reg2, composite, reg4	Permute
SHF reg1, reg2, composite, reg4	Integer Funnel Shift
FCMP reg1, reg2, composite, reg4	FP32 Compare to Zero and Select Source
ICMP reg1, reg2, composite, reg4	Integer Compare to Zero and Select Source
ISCADD reg1, reg2, composite, 5-bit lit	Scaled Integer Addition
ISCADD32I reg1, reg2, 32-bit lit, 5-bit lit	((undocumented))
BRA (CC), const/lit composite	Relative Branch
BRX (CC), const_mem_with_reg2	Relative Branch Indirect
BRX (CC), reg2, 24-bit lit	Relative Branch Indirect
CAL const/lit composite	Relative Call
PBK const/lit composite	Pre-Break
PCNT const/lit composite	Pre-continue
SSY const/lit composite	Set Synchronization Point
TEXDEPBAR 6-bit lit	((undocumented))
DSETP p2, p1, reg2, composite, p5	FP64 Set Predicate
FSETP p2, p1, reg2, composite, p5	FP32 Set Predicate
ISETP p2, p1, reg2, composite, p5	Integer Set Predicate
CSETP p2, p1, CC, p5	CC Set Predicate
PSETP p2, p1, p3, p4, p5	Predicate Set Predicate
LDG reg1, [reg2 + 11-bit lit]	Non-coherent Global Memory Load
LD reg1, [reg2 + 32-bit lit]	Load from Memory
LDL reg1, [reg2 + 24-bit lit]	Load from Local Memory
LDS reg1, [reg2 + 24-bit lit]	Load from Shared Memory
ST [reg2 + 32-bit lit], reg1	Store to Memory
STL [reg2 + 24-bit lit], reg1	Store to Local Memory
STS [reg2 + 24-bit lit], reg1	Store to Shared Memory
BPT	Breakpoint/Trap
BRK (CC)	Break
CONT (CC)	Continue
EXIT (CC)	Exit Program
MEMBAR	Memory Barrier
NOP (CC)	No Operation
RET (CC)	Return From Subroutine

Instructions for Compute Capabilities 5.x and 6.x

Instruction	Official Description
FCHK p2, reg2, composite	Single Precision FP Divide Range Check
VOTE (reg1), p6, p5	Vote Across SIMD Thread Group
LDC reg1, const_mem_with_reg2	Load Constant
MOV reg1, composite, (5-bit lit)	Move
MOV32I reg1, 32-bit lit, (4-bit lit)	((undocumented))
S2R reg1, special_reg	Move Special Register to Register
SEL reg1, reg2, composite, p5	Select Source with Predicate
TEX reg1, reg2, (reg3), 13-bit lit, 3-bit tex, 4-bit lit	Texture Fetch
TEXS reg4, reg1, reg2, (reg3), 13-bit lit, 1-bit tex, channel	Texture Fetch with scalar/non-vec4 source/destinations
TLDS reg4, reg1, reg2, (reg3), 13-bit lit, 1-bit tex, channel	Texture Load with scalar/non-vec4 source/destinations
I2I reg1, composite	Integer To Integer Conversion
I2F reg1, composite	Integer To Floating Point Conversion
F2I reg1, composite	Floating Point To Integer Conversion
F2F reg1, composite	Floating Point To Floating Point Conversion
MUFU reg1, reg2	Multi Function Operation
FLO reg1, composite	Find Leading One
POPC reg1, composite	Population count
RRO reg1, composite	Range Reduction Operator FP
FADD32I reg1, reg2, 32-bit lit	((undocumented))
FMUL32I reg1, reg2, 32-bit lit	((undocumented))
IADD32I reg1, reg2, 32-bit lit	((undocumented))
LOP32I reg1, reg2, 32-bit lit	((undocumented))
BFE reg1, reg2, composite	Bit Field Extract
DADD reg1, reg2, composite	FP64 Add
DMUL reg1, reg2, composite	FP64 Multiply
FADD reg1, reg2, composite	FP32 Add
FMUL reg1, reg2, composite	FP32 Multiply
IADD reg1, reg2, composite	Integer Addition
SHL reg1, reg2, composite	Shift Left
SHR reg1, reg2, composite	Shift Right
LOP (p7), reg1, reg2, composite	Logic Operation
BFI reg1, reg2, composite, reg5	Bit Field Insert
PRMT reg1, reg2, composite, reg5	Permute Register Pair
DFMA reg1, reg2, composite <-> reg5	FP64 Fused Multiply Add
FFMA reg1, reg2, composite <-> reg5	FP32 Fused Multiply and Add
FCMP reg1, reg2, composite, reg5	FP32 Compare to Zero and Select Source
IADD3 reg1, reg2, composite, reg5	3-input Integer Addition
ICMP reg1, reg2, composite, reg5	Integer Compare to Zero and Select Source
XMAD reg1, reg2, composite <-> reg5	Integer Short Multiply Add
SHF reg1, reg2, composite, reg5	Funnel Shift
VABSDIFF reg1, reg2, composite, reg5	((undocumented))
IMNMX reg1, reg2, composite, p5	Integer Minimum/Maximum
DMNMX reg1, reg2, composite, p5	FP64 Minimum/Maximum
FMNMX reg1, reg2, composite, p5	FP32 Minimum/Maximum
ISCADD reg1, reg2, composite, 5-bit lit	Scaled Integer Addition
ISCADD32I reg1, reg2, 32-bit lit, 5-bit lit	((undocumented))
DSET reg1, reg2, composite, p5	FP64 Compare And Set
FSET reg1, reg2, composite, p5	FP32 Compare And Set
ISSET reg1, reg2, composite, p5	Integer Compare And Set
PSET reg1, p3, p4, p5	Combine Predicates and Set
LOP3 (p7), reg1, reg2, reg3, reg5, 8-bit lit	3-input Logic Operation

LOP3 reg1, reg2, composite, reg5, 9-bit lit
 LEA (p7), reg1, reg2, 19-bit lit, (5-bit lit)
 LEA (p7), reg1, reg2, reg3, reg5, (5-bit lit)
 LEA (p7), reg1, reg2, reg3, (5-bit lit)
 PSETP p2, p1, p3, p4, p5
 DSETP p2, p1, reg2, composite, p5
 FSETP p2, p1, reg2, composite, p5
 ISETP p2, p1, reg2, composite, p5
 CSETP p2, p1, CC, p5
 BAR 8-bit lit, (19-bit lit)
 BRA (CC), const/lit composite
 CAL const/lit composite
 PBK const/lit composite
 PCNT const/lit composite
 SSY const/lit composite
 JCAL large const/lit composite
 BRX (CC), const_mem_with_reg2
 BRX (CC), reg2, 24-bit lit
 DEPBAR (sb, 6-bit lit), (bitfield)
 LD reg1, [reg2 + 32-bit lit], p8
 ST [reg2 + 32-bit lit], reg1, p9
 LDG reg1, [reg2 + 24-bit lit]
 LDL reg1, [reg2 + 24-bit lit]
 LDS reg1, [reg2 + 24-bit lit]
 STG [reg2 + 24-bit lit], reg1
 STL [reg2 + 24-bit lit], reg1
 STS [reg2 + 24-bit lit], reg1
 RED [reg2 + 20-bit lit], reg1
 NOP (CC), 16-bit lit
 BRK (CC)
 CONT (CC)
 EXIT (CC)
 RET (CC)
 SYNC (CC)

3-input Logic Operation
 Compute Effective Address
 Compute Effective Address
 Compute Effective Address
 Combine Predicates and Set Predicate
 FP64 Compare And Set Predicate
 FP32 Compare And Set Predicate
 Integer Compare And Set Predicate
 Test Condition Code and Set Predicate
 Barrier Synchronization
 Relative Branch
 Relative Call
 Pre-Break
 Pre-continue
 Set Synchronization Point
 Absolute Call
 Relative Branch Indirect
 Relative Branch Indirect
 ((undocumented))
 Load from generic Memory
 Store to generic Memory
 Load from Global Memory
 Load within Local Memory Window
 Local within Shared Memory Window
 Store to global Memory
 Store within Local or Shared Window
 Store within Local or Shared Window
 Reduction Operation on generic Memory
 No Operation
 Break
 Continue
 Exit Program
 Return From Subroutine
 Converge threads after conditional branch

References